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ABBREVIATION AND METONYMY IN SECOND NOMINATIVE INTERNET TERMS

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Abstract. Abbreviations are a grammatical phenomenon that exists in every language. The purpose of the article is to analyze abbreviations in English Internet terminology. In addition, the phenomenon of secondary nominalization in abbreviations has been studied.

Key words: abbreviation, acronym, internet terminology, linguistics, acronym, abbreviation, discourse.

Introduction

Over the past decades modern languages have exhibited a tendency towards 'economical use,' which consists in providing a maximum amount of data transmission per unit of time. In this regard, we currently observe an "explosive increase in the use of abbreviations" in languages [1]. This is especially obvious in the language of science and technology, which is characterized by a large number of different types of abbreviations and acronyms. The growing number of abbreviations, which find use in modern languages, is quite natural.

Abbreviations are an important component of many scientific and technical papers, and if one uses them effectively, they not only reduce space, but also facilitate the reading and understanding of a text. Translators often face complex sentences that are abundant in terms for which we already have well-established shortened forms. An important feature of modern scientific and technical language is the large number of abbreviations and acronyms [2].

Abbreviation is an artificial way of forming a word by connecting the elements of words. E. A. Zemskaya in his works shows that abbreviations are more relevant to written speech, because any abbreviation requires expansion (decoding), which prevents its free use [3].

Main body

An acronym is a type of alphanumeric abbreviation that consists of the initial sounds of words and is read like a regular

word. AIDS [Apple/Amiga Infected Disk Syndrome] - infected disk syndrome; RIP [Routing Information Protocol] - routing information protocol; MIME [Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions] - multipurpose Internet mail extensions; SLIP [Serial Line Internet Protocol] - Internet protocol for serial connections; NIS [Network Information Service] - network information service. In acronyms, letters are never separated by periods, as in abbreviations. Some linguists do not recognize the difference between acronym and abbreviation and use the first term for both linguistic phenomena [LES 2002: 8]. The pronunciation of acronyms and abbreviations often depends on whether or not the abbreviation is similar to a standard word, in which case it is pronounced that way. Acronyms are used less often than abbreviations in the Internet language. In the Internet language, not only phrases and word combinations, but also whole sentences are shortened, which is not characteristic of other types of discourse. For example: AWHFY (Are we having fun yet?), GMTA (Great minds think alike), ICWUM (I see what you mean), MLNW (Make love not war).

Abbreviations include clichés typical of written speech. (AAMOF (As A Matter Of Fact), AFAIK (As Far As I Know), (AFDA (A Few Days Ago), AFDB (A Few Days Back), ALAP (As Later As Possible)), (RTM(Read the manual), RYS (Read your screen)), (MLNW (Make love not war), NSD (Never say die), TBYB (Try before you buy)), (GMAB (Give me a break), LMK (Let me know)), (TFTI

(Thanks for the information), TFFT (Thanks for the thought)), (HAND (Have a nice day), RIP (Rest in peace)), (CSL (Can't Stop Laughing), BWL (Bursting With Laughter), IDBY (I Don't Believe You), DHI (Delighted to Hear It)), (AFC (Away From Computer), AATK (Always At The Keyboard)), (AFCPS (Any Fool Can Plainly See), AIAMU (And I'm A Monkey's Uncle), BAF (Brain Already Fried)), TGAL (Think Globally Act Locally), TGFTCL (Thank God For The Chat Line). has the characteristic of zero and is also seen as a homonym, for example: CU - See You / Cracking Up, CUL - See You Later / Catch You Later, WN? - What Now? / What Next? The meaning of p makes it difficult for the user to understand the meaning of this abbreviation. One of the complex aspects of abbreviations is that it is difficult to remember abbreviations made up of a large number of capital letters. The following word is a clear example of this: PCMCIA - People Can't Memorize Computer Industry Acronyms. Abbreviations provide euphemistic opportunities for using obscene words and phrases because there is some anonymity. Anonymity and invisibility to others often creates a feeling of rudeness and permission. Such ease of communication even led to the development of special network etiquette, the purpose of which was to fight "online storms". In order to avoid unpleasant consequences, in some cases the following decoding of the RTFM abbreviation was encountered - read the Friendly Guide.

The main reasons for the emergence of Internet abbreviations are, firstly, the desire to simplify and reduce the time for the process of interaction; and secondly, the desire for corporate isolation of "netizens" to create their own jargon, understandable only to the Internet community. These are. abbreviations perfectly embody one of the main principles of jargon: to define belonging to one group, for those who use the same code, who can easily solve this abbreviation. Geeks anywhere in the world are instantly recognizable by their casual conversations about ROME and RAME and

DOSe and WYSIWIG. If you do not use these words freely in speech, if you have to ask the interlocutor who tells you the abbreviations to pronounce these or those units and you need to know the meaning of these, then you do not belong to the community of computer geeks. abbreviations with the use of a dictionary (respectively, read-only memory; random access memory; disk operating system; what you see). Third, to create their own mechanisms of game communication strategies that can revive and diversify the Internet communication process. Fourthly, the extremely wide variety of abbreviations that serve to name the state of fun and laughter is due to the fact that most of the "interlocutors" aim for the main goal - fun - enjoyment in the process of communication. 'liq. Fifth, the abbreviation hides the rude, obscene element, which is forgotten in the abbreviated form, loses the effect of obscenity and becomes only an indicator of colloquial informal communication style. Sixth, an abbreviation can serve as a means of classifying information. For example, teenagers use in conversations to find out if their friends' parents are on the computer, i.e. in this case, the abbreviation performs the function of a "secret" warning system. Compare: CD9 ("Code 9") - parents around, PAW/PRW - parents watching, MOS - mother on shoulder, PIR - parent in room, P911 - parent emergency [4] .

An important part of new concepts that enter everyday communication are various types of abbreviations. Abbreviations of names related to computer languages, hardware, computer software, as well as the Internet have enriched the English language, as evidenced by the fact that they are listed in Macmillan (2002), Longman (2003) and other such dictionaries. For example, ADSL [asymmetric digital subscriber line] - asymmetric digital subscriber line, CAD / CAM [computer-aided design and computer-aided manufacturing] - computer-aided design / computer-aided manufacturing, CD [compact disc] - compact

disc, CPU [central processing unit] - central processor, DOS [disk operating system] - disk operating system, FTP [file transfer protocol] - file transfer protocol, FYI [for your information] - "for your information", GIF [graphic interchange format] - Graphic exchange format, GUI [graphic user interface] - Graphic user interface, HTML [hypertext markup language] - hypertext markup language, ISDN [Integrated Services Digital Network] - upper digital network, ISP [Internet service provider] - Internet provider, LOL [laughing out loud] - "laughing out loud", PLS [please] - "please", ROM [read-only memory] - memory for reading only, RTF [rich text format] - extended text format, SCSI [small computer system interface] - a small computer system interface, WAP [wireless application protocol] - a protocol for wireless applications [3].

As we travel the endless expanses of the Internet, we come across other wacky forms of abbreviations. Among them, the following types are popular among users: digital abbreviations, "sound" abbreviations, keyboard abbreviations, graphic abbreviations.

1) The largest group are numerical abbreviations, which use numbers instead of letters, syllables and words. It contains various combinations of letters with numbers or simply numerical codes. For example: B4N (Vue for now), T2UL (Talk to you later), W8 (Wait), 2L8 (Too late), GR8 (Great), 4YEO (For your eyes only), W3C (World Wide Web Consortium), ZSot (the Coms standing for Computer, Communications, Compatibility).

2) "Sound" abbreviations are abbreviations in which letters similar to sounds are used instead of words, for example: si (see you), r (are), cul (see you later), thx (thanks).

3) Keyboard abbreviations include abbreviations that use symbols instead of letters on a computer keyboard: sk%l (school), ki\$\$, @, etc.

4) The use of emoticons can be consid-

ered as graphic abbreviations, because they are used as symbols expressing the feelings of the participants of virtual communication: @- very happy, 0 — sad, :-0 - surprised or shocked, etc. [5].

Conclusion. Almost 20,000 new words appear in the English language each year, mainly thanks to computers and the latest technology. And although many of these words are scientific, technical or very narrow words, nevertheless, the main stream of hundreds of words is poured into colloquial speech every year. A large percentage of these words are abbreviations.

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